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Academics' Age and Scholastic Output in Federal Universities in South-South Zone of Nigeria

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Abstract

Scholarly research is crucial for academic career advancement, evaluation, appointments, ranking, and reputation of academics. This study examines the differences that exist in scholastic output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South Zone of Nigeria based on age. One research question was raised and one hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. The study adopted descriptive research design and sampled a total of 1,383 academics from a population of 7,323, using multi-stage sampling approach (purposive, simple random and cluster sampling methods). A researcher developed instrument tagged, "Academics' Scholastic Output Questionnaire" (ASOQ) validated by experts was used to obtain data for the study. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha reliability method and the coefficient 0.84 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation (SD) were used to answer the research question while the hypothesis was tested using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant difference in the scholastic output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria based on age. Based on the findings, it is recommended (among others) that older academics should provide effective mentorship for younger academics, the University Management should prioritize staff development to encourage academics, especially the younger academics to develop themselves professionally and acquire more research skills, and the Federal government as well, should make concerted efforts to reduce to the barest minimum the various challenges facing research productivity in Federal Universities in

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South-South Nigeria through sponsorship, grants, provision of internet facilities and translation of research results into policies to enhance scholastic output among academics.

Introduction

Universities are acknowledged as centers of excellence where knowledge is produced and then made available to those who need it. They are official educational institutions created by the society to produce and advance knowledge through high-caliber research outputs. The university is, strictly speaking, a community of scholars who are free to both seek and impart knowledge. Every profession has procedures in place for rating its members. Research productivity in universities is typically measured by the number of articles published in reputable journals.

In Nigerian public universities, scholastic output also known as research publication, research output or scholarly work by faculty is a benchmark for professional growth and promotion. It is traditional for universities to promote academics on the basis of their research output. It is a key factor for assessing academics, particularly in relation to tenure and advancement, pay, and other perks of the job. Hence, the adage "publish or perish" that is common in the academic setting. Hence, the role of academics is not limited to teaching. Their research output is of great importance to them, the students, institution and the nation at large. The importance of scholastic output of academics cannot be ignored in any way. It may be said that it is the major indicator of an academic's quality and the determining factor of academics' advancement. Staff with low research output may suffer delayed promotions, may not be recommended for appointments, may lose integrity and respect and may eventually lead to depression (Etudor-Eyo, Okon and Nunayon, 2023). This affects not only the concerned academics but other staff, students, the university and the society. The quality and quantity of an institution's research is one of the yardsticks for measuring its academic accomplishment and excellence (Samuel, Ogunlade and Onasanya, 2018).

The government has worked hard to increase both the quality and quantity of academics' research output through, among other things, research funding, staff training and development programs, scholarships, and infrastructure. Some universities work with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) to focus research initiatives from which they would also profit. International organizations like the World Bank granted a

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\$131 million grant at their 2019 Board meeting to increase their assistance to Benin, Gambia, Niger, Nigeria, and Togo in order to provide high quality education, training, and applied research in a few important disciplines (World Bank, 2019). Considering the economic significance of research, individuals have also provided research grants to universities, research institutes, and other organizations to increase research productivity.

The issue of weak academic research production in universities has not been resolved despite attempts by the government, individuals, businesses, and NGOs. Poor academic productivity among academics at Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria continues to be a problem. Some researchers, including Yusuf (2005), Samuel, Ogunlade and Onasanya (2018), Subramanian and Nammalvar (2017); Altbach (2015), Pacheco-Vega (2013), Lariviere and Costas (2016), and Spicer (2015), have attributed the poor scholastic output by academics to factors such as inadequate and inconsistent university funding, a lack of facilities (for instance, internet facilities), a lack of research motivation, rising workloads, etc.

Age describes how old a person is at a particular point in time. It is defined as the measure of the time elapsed from date of live birth to a specific point in time, usually the date of collection of the data (Lally and Valentine-French, 2019). Increase in age of an individual usually affects the various developmental changes and subsequently affects every area of his/her performance (Ukueneze, 2007). Studies have shown that certain abilities decline with age, but not necessarily certain skills. Research has demonstrated that different abilities tend to follow relatively independent paths over the life cycle. Productivity potential in the workplace generally depends on one's physical and mental abilities, education, and job experience. These abilities and experiences are widely thought to eventually influence job performance and the productivity of employees. The outcomes of studies on the relationship between age and productivity depend on how the job performance dimension is measured. Academics who are older in age may not be very productive in terms of research output as their younger counterparts. Some researches show that productivity increases with age, but after a certain time it begins to decline (Abramo, D'Angelo, and Costa, 2019).

There are, however, arguments suggesting that older academics might exhibit lower research productivity than their younger colleagues for various reasons. Yet, the argument still appears inconclusive. While the researcher observed that many of these

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studies on age of academics and scholastic output were carried out outside Nigeria, some of the studies within Nigeria were done in State and private universities. Also, some of the studies were carried out based on the location of the researcher. In addition, most of the works addressed the constraints of research productivity like poor funding, institutional challenges and others amongst lecturers. This has created a gap which this study undertook to fill. Thus, the study examined the differences that exist in scholastic output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South zone of Nigeria based on age.

Theoretical Framework

The theory used for this study is Tajfel and Turner's Social Identity Theory proposed in 1979. This theory focuses on individuals' behaviours within a group. The theory views social identity as the interplay between personal and social identities. The theory also considers the consequences of personal and social identities for individual perceptions and group behaviour. Tajfel (1981) defined social identity as that part of an individual's self-concept which is derived from his knowledge of his membership of a social group (or groups), together with the value and emotional significance attached to that membership. Tajfel and Turner (1981) further explained that social identity also involves the concept of identity which is based on self-categorization wherein persons within social structures assign labels to others and themselves as a manner of recognizing each other as occupants of specific roles. Roles they saw as basic, stable components of structured society that are culturally defined and learned. Herein, demographic like age (role) serves as the self-identification of one's self as young or old. Central to the concept of identity is the incorporation of the meanings and expectations associated with a self-accepted role. This process of self-labeling, acceptance and incorporation guides behaviour. Labels, roles, meanings and expectations are set by the structured society and culture; and how the society in which the individual (academics) belong see their age (young or old) is important.

The relevance of Social Identity theory to this study is that it illustrates how academics relate within the university. The theory can be associated with the personal and social identities of academics within the university. Labels, roles, meanings, and expectations are set by individuals and the university system. Such roles include the age of academics. Expectations from the university may involve quality research output

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while expectation of academics may include promotions, salary payments, appointments and so on. Self-categorization of academics within the university can enable them recognize the specific roles of others within the university. The roles, expectations and demands of the academic community is able to influence academics despite their ages. It appears that some aspects of identity play a large role in the actualization of educational goals and should be engaged in order to foster academics research output in the universities.

Literature Review

Aging means to become old; to show the effects or the characteristics of increasing age or to acquire a desirable quality (such as mellowness or ripeness) by standing undisturbed for some time (Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary, 2021). Age is the measure of the time elapsed from date of live birth to a specific point in time, usually the date of collection of the data.

Lally and Valentine-French, (2019) outline types of ages as follows:

- i) **Chronological Age:** This is the number of years from the birth of an individual. Ever felt older than your chronological age? Some days we might “feel” like we are older, especially if we are not feeling well, are tired, or are stressed out. We might notice that a peer seems more emotionally mature than we are, or that they are physically more capable.
- ii) **Biological Age:** This concept of age examines how quickly the body is aging. Several factors determine the rate at which our body ages. These are: nutrition, level of physical activity, sleeping habits, smoking, alcohol consumption, how mental stress is handled, and the genetic history of one’s ancestors, to name but a few.
- iii) **Psychological Age:** This is one’s psychologically adaptive capacity compared to others of their chronological age. This includes an individual’s cognitive capacity along with their emotional beliefs about how old they are. An individual who has cognitive impairments might be 20 years of age yet has the mental capacity of an eight-year-old while a 70-year-old might be travelling to new countries, taking courses at a college, or starting a new business. Compared to others of one’s age group, one may be more or less adaptive and excited to meet new challenges. In a psychological age parameter, one is as young or old as

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he/she feels.

- iv) **Social Age:** One's social age is based on the social norms of his/her culture and the expectations his/her culture has for people of their age group. People's culture often reminds them whether they are "on target" or "off target" for reaching certain social milestones such as completing their education, moving away from home, having children, or retiring from work. However, there have been arguments that social age is becoming less relevant in the 21st century (Neugarten, in Lally and Valentine-French, (2019).

According to Kalla (2006), the age concept has recently emerged in various fields - gerontological, psychological, futurological, demographic, legal, political, and cultural contexts as an interest of research. Diversity studies have included age among race, gender, creed, ethnicity, background, education, function, and personality differences. At the same time, while a vast number of organizational studies have covered almost every angle of the leadership theme (Åhman, 2003), the concept of age has largely been ignored. The almost untouched area of the conceptualisation of age, and as a consequence of it, the discursive perception of a leader as well as his/her capabilities needs to be explored and unmasked further. This is particularly important due to the topical importance of age understanding in emergence of the huge demographic changes. At the same time, lifelong training/learning provides individuals with adequate knowledge throughout their lives, and the march of powerful new technologies will probably have greater impact on human life and its expectancy, and also to the aging process which can be slowed down or even reversed (Featherstone and Hepworth, in Kalla 2006) than we can even imagine. Biotechnology is marching to such extreme fluid stages where "leakiest" distinction or boundaries will be those between the human and animal, the human and the machine, and the physical and the non-physical...." (Wei in Kalla, 2006 P.46, 161). It is also essential to understand age due to its human and organizational significance. Age is a human attribute that has long been taken for granted. However, we know very little about the age beneath the skin and beyond the body.

Older age and the age concept need to be explored from discourses of age that have been constructed over social practices and time since they are ascribed to the leader's identity, especially when using it in relation to the capability perception. Biases, that obviously exist should be first recognized and then made visible so that those biases

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could be overcome. Learning to know age would be a leap to a more neutral, more justified, more complete and more whole perception of age in determining leaders' capabilities in the post-modern organization, and preparing societies to encounter inevitable changes more efficiently. Over in Okiki (2013) maintains that research productivity of academics slightly decreased with age. Bland and Berquist in Okiki (2013) also had observed that the average productivity of academic members drop with age but many senior academics remain active and that there is no significant evidence that age determines a drop in productivity.

North, Zewotir and Murray (2014) believe that younger members of staff could possibly be more research active than older members of staff. This is because they are ambitiously trying to build up a research profile whilst older staff members most likely have already attained higher academic status and could further be more involved in administrative duties. It is important therefore, to see the effect that age may have had on the level of research output. Some researches show that production increases with age, but after a certain time it begins to decline. Abramo et al. (2016) explained this effect in research output as an inverted U, due to two opposite effects: the great amount of innovative ideas during the professional development stage of the researches and the increasing risk of becoming professionals with out-dated skills and difficulties to find new research themes at the decline stage. In the same way, Backes-Gellner and Schilnghoff (2004) found that the productivity of professors tends to decrease after being promoted as a full professor. Some studies concluded that there is a significant relationship between research output and age (Hedjazi and Behravan, 2011; Khahil and Khahil, 2019). However, the results are still contradictory because other studies like that of Bland et al. (2005) did not find statistical evidence that there was difference in faculty research productivity due to age.

Also, there is a general recognition that greater education can lead to better productivity in old age. Some literature suggests that there are multiple factors which indicate higher job performance amongst younger workers. Most of these studies argue that workers' health tends to deteriorate due to health issues like diseases, body strength, depression, etc. over the life cycle; and cognitive abilities also generally decrease with age which may result in lower productivity level of older workers. Young people are thought to be more motivated to exert increased and higher effort at work since they want to impress their employer (Grund and Westergaard-Nielsen, 2005). In contrast, older people might be less enthusiastic in on-the-job training or skills improvement since the incentives in terms of promotion and so forth diminish with age. Those closer to retirement may have less incentive to learn work related skills and at the same time the

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ability to learn new skills also appears to deteriorate with age. Various studies found an inverted U-shaped work performance profile. Workers in their 30s and 40s have the highest productivity levels, while workers above the age of 50 have lower productivity levels than their younger colleagues in spite of their higher wage level (De Hek and Van Vuuren, 2011). Daveri and Maliranta (2007) indicate that the impact of these age-related factors also have an inverse U-shaped relationship with productivity in the Finnish electronics industry and this U increases in prominence in the forest industry and the production of machinery and equipment industry. Based on the concepts reviewed, age could affect the research output of academics. This study will examine the difference in research output of academics based on age.

Empirical studies on age and scholastic outputs of academics are few, but considerable effort has been made to review related literatures. Age has been studied in numerous works, with conflicting results. Many studies about productivity have indicated that the relationship between publication and age is not linear, although the overall rate of publication generally declines with age (Teodorescu, 2000). According to Over in Okiki (2015), research productivity of academics slightly decreases with age. Bland and Berquist in Okiki (2015) also observed that the average productivity of academic members drop with age but many senior academics remain active and that there is no significant evidence that age determines a drop in productivity.

In Nigeria, Anyaogu and Mabawonku (2014) also examined demographic variables as correlates of lecturers' research productivity in Faculties of Law in Nigerian universities. The descriptive survey research design was adopted. The multistage sampling technique was used to select 414 out of 905 lecturers from 16 faculties of Law in 29 federal and state universities across the 6 geo-political zones of Nigeria. A questionnaire was used, three research questions were answered, and one hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, Pearson product moment correlation, and multiple regressions. Based on multiple regressions analysis, the result shows that demographic variables such as age, designation, and years of experience have significant positive relationship with research productivity of law lecturers.

Arshad and Ameen (2017) carried out a study to investigate the relationship of academic staff's use of e-journals with demographic and profession related variables. The quantitative survey method was used to achieve the objectives of the study. The population of the study included academic staff of 12 faculties of the University of

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Punjab. Self-administered questionnaire was distributed to 841 regular and contractual academic staff members with a response rate of 54%. The results of the study found that the respondents' frequency of e-journals use was significantly related to their discipline, age, education, internet use, e-literacy skills and research output. However, e-journals use was not significantly related to their official position and gender. It is a valuable study as it comprehensively investigated correlation of certain variables with academic staff's use of e-journals in Pakistani perspective.

Another study by Remery et al. (2003) analysed a survey of 1007 Dutch business leaders and personnel managers and found that older individuals are more likely to be perceived as less productive when the share of senior employees is higher. Research shows that while job experience improves productivity for several years, there does come a point at which further experience no longer has a positive effect. Ilmakunnas, Maliranta and Vainiomäki (1999) assessed a broad sample of Finnish manufacturing employees, and found that job duration improves job performance for only up to 3.8 years. On the other hand, other studies based on different research designs have found that professional expertise developed over the years of practice and experience, can attenuate potential negative relationships between age and performance dimensions (Hess and Auman 2001; Thornton and Dumke 2005; Wilson et al., 2006). Also there is a general recognition that greater education can lead to better productivity in old age. Some literatures suggest that there are multiple factors which indicate higher job performance amongst younger workers. Most of these studies argue that workers' health tends to deteriorate over time and cognitive abilities also generally decrease with age which may result in a lower productivity level of older workers. Young people are thought to be more motivated to exert increased and higher effort at work since they want to impress their employer (Grund and Westergaard-Nielsen, 2005).

In contrast, older people might be less enthusiastic in on-the-job training or skills improvement since the incentives in terms of promotion and so forth diminish with age. Those closer to retirement may have less incentive to learn work related skills and at the same time the ability to learn new skills also deteriorate with age (Hayward et al., 1997). Employers might be more reluctant to invest in training older workers because they have a shorter period of time to benefit from on-the-job training (Brooke 2003; Prskawetz et al., 2006).

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Moreover, when older employees take part in training, their participation seems to be less effective compared to younger employees (Gobel and Zwick, 2010). Thus, a decline in relative productivity of older employees is expected in sectors that need continuous training efforts. In general, strong decreases in productivity are observed after the age of 50 (Dostie 2006; Grund and Westergaard-Nielsen, 2005; Hellerstein and Neumark, 2004; Prskawetz et al., 2006). Boot (1995) studied age-earnings profiles of British workers in physically demanding jobs during the first half of the 19th century. His study indicated that men reach their peak earnings in their early 30s, and wages decrease substantially from around 40 years of age. Dostie (2006), Lallemand and Rycx (2009), and Van Ours and Stoeldraijer (2010) investigated the impact of the firm's worker composition on production which include the correlations between the firm's age composition and its production. Various studies found an inverted U-shaped work performance profile.

Workers in their 30s and 40s have the highest productivity levels, while workers above the age of 50 have lower productivity levels than their younger colleagues in spite of their higher wage level (De Hek and Van Vuuren, 2011). Daveri and Maliranta (2007) indicate that the impact of these age-related factors also have an inverse U-shaped relationship with productivity in the Finnish electronics industry and this U increases in prominence in the forest industry and the production of machinery and equipment industry. Examples of the earlier proponents of an inverted U-shaped relationship between age and productivity are Sturman (2003) and Avolio et al. (1990). Other studies do not find support for an inverse U-shaped form of the age-productivity profile.

Another study was conducted by Subramanian and Nammalvar, (2017) on Age, Gender and Research Productivity: A Study of Speech and Hearing Faculty in India. A cross-sectional longitudinal study was carried out with the data set covering 1174 Research Productive Units (RPU) from 1995-96 to 2014-15 relating to scientific publications. It involved 114 teaching faculty in speech and hearing institutions. The findings of this study revealed that research performance score for scientific publications showed two peaks, in the age group >55 years and another in the age group of < 30 years, the former being the higher of the peaks. Within the study by Subramanian and Nammalvar (2017) on Publication Productivity among Scientists, the following studies were cited: Lehman in Subramanian, and Nammalvar, (2017), published evidence that scientists' major contributions occur in their late 30s or early 40s, and

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thereafter decline. In subsequent documentation, Lehman in Subramanian, and Nammalvar (2017), verified his observations, and showed further that the age peak occurred earlier in abstract disciplines (such as mathematics and theoretical physics) and later in more empirically based fields (such as geology and biology). Moreover, he observed that the age peak is sharper for major contributions and achievements, and flatter for minor scientific accomplishments.

Following Lehman in Subramanian, and Nammalvar (2017), Pelz and Andrews in Subramanian, and Nammalvar (2017) found a productivity peak in scientists' late 30s and early 40s; but they also observed a second peak ten to fifteen yrs later at age 50. Thus, in contrast to the continuing decline of Lehman's observations, Pelz and Andrews found a two-peaked curve of age and productivity. Cole in Subramanian, and Nammalvar (2017) on the other hand, reports a slightly curvilinear relationship between age and quantity of publications for a cross-section of academics in six scientific fields. Across fields, he finds that publication rates rise gradually with age, peak in the late 30s or early 40s, and then drop off. Additional longitudinal data on mathematics, which allow him to disentangle age and cohort effects, show the same pattern as his cross-sectional data: the relationship between age and productivity is slightly curvilinear, but productivity does not differ significantly with age. Kyvik in Subramanian, and Nammalvar (2017), summarizes the findings from previous studies as follows: (a) the relationship between age and the number of publication is curvilinear where productivity expands with increasing age and reaches a peak when the scientists are in the late thirties and early forties after which it declines; (b) those scientists who are more productive at a younger age will continue to be productive as they grow older; (c) in some cases two peaks are observed, the first and highest in their late thirties and early forties and another around 60; (d) there are vast differences between various disciplines with regard to the relationship between age and scientific publishing.

Kotrlik, Bartlett, Higgins and Williams (2002) in a study using a random sample of 228 college and university agricultural education faculty members in the United States, concluded that age does not significantly affect research productivity. Williams, Bartlett, Kotrlik, Higgins (2001) and Ramsden (1994) also observed that there was no association between age and research productivity.

It is worthy of note that most of these studies on age of academics and their scholastic output were carried out outside Nigeria. Moreover, most of the works

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addressed the constraints of research productivity amongst lecturers like poor or lack of funding, environmental constraints, institutional challenges and so on. Again, some of the studies were carried out based on the location of the researcher. It was also observed that many of the studies used other sub-variables not present in the study. This has created a gap which this study has undertaken to fill. Hence, the study examined the differences that exist in scholastic output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South Zone of Nigeria based on their ages.

Statement of the Problem

Scholarly research is crucial for academic career advancement, evaluation, appointments, ranking, and reputation. Academics are expected to keep up with scholarship, particularly through research and publications. Despite this assumption, it has been found that many academics lack the motivation to contribute to the creation and publication of high-caliber research publications. This situation has caused delayed promotions /stagnation, denied tenures, and benefits among many academics. It has also caused loss of relevance in the fields of specialization of such academics as they have not been able to keep abreast with recent discoveries in their fields. Efforts made by the Federal Government, NGOs and individuals have proved abortive. In addition to the aforementioned, colleges are negatively impacted by the low intellectual output of academics. For instance, one of the key metrics used to rate universities around the world is the productivity of academic researchers; and no Federal University in South-South Nigeria has currently been listed among the top 15 universities in Africa between 2016 and 2022 because of low or poor academic researches.

It is in this light that the researcher asked, ‘Could the poor scholastic output among academics exist as a result of their ages?’ Some new studies are beginning to emphasize on demographic factors of academics such as age as contributing to scholastic productivity in universities, although many previous studies declare financial deficiency as the prevalent constraint on scholastic output of academics in universities. It is against this backdrop, that the researcher examined the difference in scholastic output of academics based on their ages in Federal Universities in South-South Zone of Nigeria.

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Research Question: What is the difference in scholastic output of Academics in Federal Universities in South-South zone of Nigeria based on their ages?

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in research output of Academics in Federal Universities in South- South zone of Nigeria based on their ages.

Research Methods

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The area of study was Akwa Ibom State. A sample of 1,383 academics was sampled from a population of 7,323 using multi-stage sampling approach (purposive, simple random and cluster sampling methods). A researcher developed instrument tagged, “Academics’ Scholastic Output Questionnaire” (ASOQ) validated by experts was used to obtain data for the study. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to establish the reliability coefficient of the instrument and was established as 0.84. Mean and standard deviation (SD) were used to answer the research question while the hypothesis was tested using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance.

Table1: Means and Standard Deviations Showing the Difference in Scholastic Output of Academics Based on Age

Age	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
< or= 30	20.05	20	8.04
30-39	16.72	208	6.78
40-49	19.34	269	7.57
50-59	18.55	319	5.19
60 and above	19.66	108	5.93

Source: Field Data (2022).

N= 924

Result in Table 1 shows descriptive statistics on scholastic output of academics based on age. It reveals that academics that are less than or equal to 30 years of age perform better in their scholastic outputs than others by their mean score with the highest mean score of 20.05. While academics that are 60 years and above have a higher mean score of 19.66 than those who are between 40 and 49 years, academics within the

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age category of 50-59 with mean score of 18.55, have a higher mean score than academics who are 30-39 years with a mean score of 16.72. This shows that academics that are less than or equal to 30 years differ in their scholastic outputs from academics in other age categories. The result also shows that the standard deviations of the scores for the academics are above 1 (8.04, 6.78, 7.57, 5.19 and 5.93). This shows there is a difference in the scholastic output of academics based on age. Therefore, academics differ in their scholastic output based on age. To determine the significance of mean difference in the scholastic output of academics, the researcher applied the statistical tool, ANOVA and the result is presented in Table 2

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the scholastic output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria based on age.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance of the difference in Academics' Scholastic Output based on Age

	Sum	of	Mean				Decision at
Source of Variation	Squares	df	Square	F-Cal.	F-Crit.	Sig.	p<.05
Between Groups	1041.729	4	260.432	6.22	2.37	.00	*
Within Groups	38457.472	919	41.847				
Total	39499.201	923					

Source: Field Data (2022)

* = significant ($p < 0.05$)

The result in Table 2 reveals that the calculated F-value of 6.22 is greater than the critical value of 2.37 at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom of 4 and 919. Consequently, since p value is less than 0.05, this indicates a significant difference in scholastic output of academics based on age. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in research output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria based on age is rejected. That means there is significant difference in research output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria based on age.

Based on the result above, further analysis was carried out using the Scheffe Post-Hoc Analysis to find out where the significance exists. The result as presented in Table

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4.9 and 4.10 reveal that the significant difference in scholastic output of academics lie in ages 30 - 39 and 60 and above. It may be deduced from the analysis therefore, that the scholastic output of academics that fall in the age categories of 30 - 39 and 60 and above differ from other academics in other age categories.

Table 3: Scheffe Post-Hoc Analysis for Age

Age	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	
30-39	208	16.7196	
50-59	319	18.5549	
40-49	269	19.3395	
60 and above	108	19.6574	
< or= 30	20	20.0500	
Sig.		.054	

Source: Field Data (2022) Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

Table 4: Scheffe Post-Hoc Multiple Comparisons Analysis for Age

) Age	(J) Age	Mean Difference			95% Confidence Interval	
		(I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
< or = 30	30-39	3.33045	1.51444	.305	-1.3439	8.0048
	40-49	.71047	1.49931	.994	-3.9171	5.3381
	50-59	1.49514	1.49115	.909	-3.1073	6.0976
	60 and above	.39259	1.57475	1.000	-4.4679	5.2530
30-39	< or= 30	-3.33045	1.51444	.305	-8.0048	1.3439
	40-49	-2.61998*	.59729	.001	-4.4635	-.7764
	50-59	-1.83531*	.57652	.039	-3.6147	-.0559
	60 and above	-2.93786*	.76724	.006	-5.3059	-.5698
40-49	< or= 30	-.71047	1.49931	.994	-5.3381	3.9171
	30-39	2.61998*	.59729	.001	.7764	4.4635
	50-59	.78467	.53549	.709	-.8681	2.4375
	60 and above	-.31788	.73691	.996	-2.5924	1.9566

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50-59	< or= 30	-1.49514	1.49115	.909	-6.0976	3.1073
	30-39	1.83531*	.57652	.039	.0559	3.6147
	40-49	-.78467	.53549	.709	-2.4375	.8681
	60 and above	-1.10255	.72018	.673	-3.3254	1.1203
60 and above	< or= 30	-.39259	1.57475	1.000	-5.2530	4.4679
	30-39	2.93786*	.76724	.006	.5698	5.3059
	40-49	.31788	.73691	.996	-1.9566	2.5924
	50-59	1.10255	.72018	.673	-1.1203	3.3254

Source: Field Data (2022). *. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of the study from the research question revealed that academics in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria differed in their scholastic output based on age. This means that academics of different age categories differed in their scholastic output.

Also, data analysis for the hypothesis indicates that there is significant difference in the scholastic output of academics based on age. Consequently, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in academics scholastic output based on age is rejected.

The result of the Scheffe's Post Hoc Analysis revealed that the significant difference in scholastic output of academics lies in ages 30 - 39 and 60 and above. The turnout of this result may be attributable to the fact that academics who are 60 years and above may have had more exposures to research funding, grants, good mentorship and personal determinations to succeed right from when they were younger in the profession. Also, academics in the age group bracket, 30-39 are academics who may be new in the profession and are ambitious about growing fast in the profession and building research profile. This passion motivates them to be involved in more research activities.

The finding of this study is in line with that conducted by Subramanian and Nammalvar (2017) on Age, Gender and Research Productivity. The findings revealed that research performance score of academic staff is higher in age group greater than 55 years and another in the age group of less than 30 years, with the former being the higher

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of the peaks. Kyvik in Subramanian and Nammalvar (2017) also opines that academics who are more productive at a younger age will continue to be productive as they grow older. This is supported by Levin and Stephan (2011), who report that a person's age at first publication affects consequent research productivity and that if academic lecturers submit research for their first publication at a young age, then it is more likely that they will produce more at future points in time. This research finding is also in line with that carried out by Igiri et al. (2021), whose study revealed that there is a correlation between age and research productivity. Another study that supports the finding of the present study is that carried out by Jung (2014), who found a significant relationship between middle age (approximately 35-55 years) and higher research engagement and productivity, while others like Kwick (2018) and Vuong, Napier, Ho, Nguyen, Vuong, Pham and Nguyen (2017) revealed that older age is correlated with more research output. Based on the findings of the study, it is revealed that there is significant difference in scholastic output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria based on their ages.

Conclusion / Recommendations

The issue of weak academic research production in universities has not been resolved despite attempts by the government, individuals, businesses, and NGOs. Poor academic productivity among academics at Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria continues to be a problem. This work has shown several studies carried out based on the location of the researchers in order to ascertain the influencing factor on academics output; other works addressed the constraints of research productivity like poor funding, institutional challenges, etc., while nothing has been done in relation to age and scholastic output. This study therefore, evaluated the differences that exist in scholastic output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South zone of Nigeria based on age, and the findings reveal that there is a significant difference in scholastic output of academics in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria based on their ages.

Based on the finding of this study, it is recommended that the University Management should encourage exposure of researchers through sponsorship to local, national, and international conferences and workshops. This will enhance publishing within and outside Nigeria. Also, older academics should provide good mentorship to younger academics to encourage scholastic productivity.

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